

Evaluation of stable fracture phenomena in FRP(SMC)
using Surface Crack Density

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ABSTRACT

The stable fracture phenomena in FRP(SMC) have been investigated experimentally. The change of the fracture toughness value J and the stable cracks growth due to increase the applied stress levels are studied using the test pieces of compact tension type. The fracture toughness value J_{in} at beginning of stable crack from the notch tip is measured by the method of the elastic-plastic fracture toughness test. And it is confirmed that the value J_{in} can be determined by a new parameter "Crack Density" that is calculated with quantity of the length and the number of the surface cracks observed on the specimen and the "the size of damage area" at the notch tip.

KEY WORD: Short fiber composite; Fracture Toughness; Mode I; Crack propagation; Failure mechanism

1. INTRODUCTION

FRP(SMC) is a typical short fiber reinforced plastics. This material has a quasi-isotropic properties and it has been well-known that this property is caused by the fact that short fibers are distributed uniformly toward every direction. Such orientation is assumed to improve the fracture toughness of the material and further prevent the material from brittle fracture such as an unidirectional CFRP.[1,2] In this study, the fracture toughness test on FRP(SMC) is conducted using the test pieces of the compact-tension type. Growth of stable cracks from a notch and the change of the fracture toughness values according to increase the load are investigated. Based on these results, the elastic-plastic fracture toughness value J_{in} when the stable crack has started which is used as a index of the fracture toughness is specified.

Table 1(A) and (B) Compositions and Mechanical properties of used SMC

(A) Compositions

Composition	Per hundred
Resin (U.P.)	100
E-glass fiber	92
Filler (CaCO ₃)	100
Release agent	7.2
Catalyst	1.0
Thickener (Mgo)	0.8

(B) Mechanical Properties

	before Knee	after Knee
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	11.00	3.55
U.T.S. (MPa)	92.1	
Poisson's ratio	0.30	0.17
Density (g/cm ³)	1.78	

Development of an new method for measurement of the fracture toughness was attempted. The author carried out the fatigue tests on the same SMC and pointed out that the number and the length of cracks observed on the surface of the test piece has a close relation with its fatigue mechanical degradation.[3-4] The relation between the parameter, the "Crack Density" that is the total sum of crack lengths per unit area and the fracture toughness was investigated. As the obtained results, it is made clear that "Crack density" shows good correspondence to both the change of the stable crack and the fracture toughness value incidental to it. Furthermore, it is pointed out that the fracture toughness value strongly depend on the size of damaged area observed in the vicinity of notch tip. From these facts, it is pointed out that degree of the progress of fracture of SMC can be estimated by observing the status of the surface cracks.

2. MATERIAL AND TESTING METHOD

The composition and properties of material of used SMC are shown in Table 1 (A) and (B) respectively. The compact tensile test pieces shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. Shape and Dimension of test piece

are used in accordance with JSME S 001.[5] Since it is impossible to make natural crack in SMC artificially, the conditions of notch are made constant by drilling holes of $\phi = 0.8$ mm. The tensile testing speed is kept constant, 1 mm/min. The crack opening displacements (COD) is obtained from the relative displacement of two supporting pins. The tests are conducted under a constant temperature of $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and the humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. The fracture toughness value J is calculated by Rice's formula ($J = 2A'/(B*t)$). Where, A' is the area above the load-displacement curve and B and t are the length and thickness of the ligament respectively. About 100 test pieces were used in these tests.

The amount of growth of this stable crack is observed in the following procedure. First, the tension is applied until the specified load is reached, then the load quickly reduced by about 10% and that condition is kept for a while. Under that condition, writing ink is sprayed into the notch tip and paint simultaneously ink on the surface of the test pieces to color the cracks. Then, the load is reduced to zero and ink is thoroughly dried. Thereafter, the tensile load is applied until the test piece is completely broken. The length of the stable cracks is measured from the trace of infiltration of ink observed on the fractured surface(See Figure 2). And the quantity of surface cracks is indicated with "Crack Density (C.D.)" that is the total length of cracks in the measured area ($\sum L_i / A$ where L_i denotes the length of crack and A is the measured area which is enclosed by the broken line in Figure 1).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Evaluation of fracture toughness and stable crack growth of SMC

The method of evaluation of the fracture toughness of FRP must be chosen with distinction in accordance with the characteristics of the material. For instance, in case of CFRP in which carbon fibers whose adhesive strength is very small is used, evaluation of the delamination strength becomes necessary. And measurement of the fracture toughness value G_{Ic} are often made by using the test pieces of DCL-type on the mode I. On the other hand, for other types of the mode I, the "three-point-bending test method" or the "compact-tension method" are generally employed. Particularly for FRP which has isotropic mechanical properties and "knee" behavior that resembles the yielding phenomenon clearly occurs, evaluation by the fracture toughness value J_{Ic} is tried using the test pieces of compact type.[6] In this study, the fracture toughness tests for SMC were conducted using the compact-tension method.

Figure 2 is the illustration on the fractured surface. From the plan, it is known that the surface consists of the relatively smooth surface that has been generated from the notch and rough surfaces composed of numerous pull-out strands. This smooth plane is what was made by the stable crack growth and the length of stable crack growth D_a is determined by it. The relation between Δa and COD is shown in Figure 3. At the time when COD has reached

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of fracture surface

Figure 3. Relation between Stable crack length and Crack opening displacement

about 0.2 mm, the growth of crack starts and gradually grows until the value of COD reaches 0.5 mm. Then, COD has exceed 0.5 mm, the length of stable cracks grows rapidly.

3.2 Crack resistance curve (R-curve) in the used SMC

Figure 4 shows the relation between the stable crack length Δa and the fracture toughness value J (R-curve). From this diagram, it is known that J value rises as a whole as the length of the crack grows while showing wide dispersion. These data are divided into three groups. The first lot includes the data of the length of the crack from 0 to 0.7 mm and is named group I and second lot is called Group II and covers the length of 1.2 mm and

above. In so doing, as the data of Δa lie between 0.7 mm and 1.2 mm are difficult to judge which group they belong, they are deemed to be included in both groups. As result of investigation on the relation between the both with respect to the data of Group I, 0.74 is gained as the correlation coefficient. The relation is represented by the empirical formula of $J = 6.6 * \Delta a + 1.1$ (KN/m). Also, with respect to the data of Group II, the correlation coefficient of 0.63 is gained and the relation of $J = 4.5 * \Delta a + 3.3$ exists. The intersection of these two straight lines is given at $\Delta a = 1$ mm and the fracture toughness value $J = 7.8$ KN/m.

In the meantime, in the case of metallic material, the crack resistance curve is composed of two straight lines which are called the blunting line and the stable crack growth curve. Although there is a difference between the metallic material and SMC that while the blunting line of metal starts from the origin or from zero for both the length of stable crack and the fracture toughness value, J value of SMC starts from 1.1 KN/m, the curves for these two materials each other very well. Using the same method as in the case of metallic material, namely, from the intersection of two straight lines shown in Figure 4, the fracture toughness value J_{in} at the time when stable fracture started is determined. The value J_{ic} thus gained is 7.8 KN/m. The COD value at this time is 0.8 mm.

In the case of metallic material, it is generally accepted that the fracture toughness value J_{in} depends upon the amount of the plastic behavior that is formed at the vicinity of the notch tip. In SMC, however, no plastic deformation that is observed in metallic material exists. Therefore, the author directed their attention to the microscopic cracks

Figure 4. Crack resistance curve on used SMC

Figure 5. (A), (B), (C) and (D). Traced Surface cracks observed on some test pieces on a single sheet at three load levels (from (A) to (C)) and Diameter (D_p) of damage area in front of notch tip on (D)

that generate around the tip of the notch as absorbing mechanism of the destruction energy for SMC material taking the place of plastic behavior.

3.3 Evaluation of fracture toughness value by surface cracks

Beamont et al. theoretically introduced the relation between the cracks within the material and the spring constant.[7] The author et al. conducted the fatigue tests for SMC and pointed out that the cracks observed on the surface of the test specimen has a close relation with its mechanical degradation. [3-4] In consideration of these facts, investigations were made on the generation of cracks on the surface around the notch tip for the case of the fracture toughness test. Cracks that are observed on the surface of the test piece will be called "Surface cracks" hereinafter. In order to make clear the status of generation of cracks, the surface cracks observed on the test pieces of a plural number are traced on a single sheet of drawing and are presented in Figure 5(A)-(C). It is confirmed that the number and the length of surface cracks increase parallel to the direction of the notch as the loading level rises between Figure 5 (A) to (B). Furthermore, as the maximum load is approached, a few cracks that are

Figure 6. Relation between Crack density and Stable crack length

located at the farthest place begin to grow forming a circular shape and eventually they are connected mutually(See Figure 5(C)).

As the quantitative method of the evaluation of the surface cracks, the crack density(C.D.) which the authors have been recommended as the method to measure the status of generation of cracks through the static tests and fatigue tests up to now is going to employed (See section 2). Figure 6 shows the relation between the density of cracks and the length of the stable crack. It is confirmed that there exists a very strong correlation whose coefficient is 0.85 and the relation $C.D. = 0.09 * \Delta a$ holds good. Upon getting this result, the relation between the fracture toughness value and surface cracks is investigated. Figure 7 presented it. Similar to the case of the crack resistance curve (R-curve), it is known that the data can

Figure 7. Relation between Fracture toughness value and Crack density

be represented by two straight lines. These straight lines are calculated by the method of least squares.

The data of C.D. values are divided into Group I whose values are about 0.07 mm/mm^2 or below and group II whose values are 0.1 mm/mm^2 or above. As the same of of the case of R-curve, the data of C.D. which lie between 0.07 to 0.1 mm/mm^2 are deemed to be included in both groups. The correlation coefficient of 0.83 is gained for the group I and the empirical formula is given by $J = 83.8 * \text{C.D.} + 1.2$ and the correlation coefficient of 0.61 is gained for the group II and the formula becomes $J = 41.9 * \text{C.D.} + 4.8$. Then, the fracture toughness value $J_{in'}$ at the intersection of these two straight lines becomes 8.2 KN/m . Although this fracture toughness value $J_{in'}$ is 5% higher than the fracture toughness value J_{in} , the both values are very close each other. From these facts, the conclusion is reached that by observing the surface cracks it is possible to estimate the degree of damage and furthermore to calculate the fracture toughness value J_{in} .

3.4 Relation between the size of damage area and the fracture toughness value

Investigation is made on the size of the area close to the tip of the notch over which the surface cracks are generated. The range over which cracks

Figure 8. Relation between Diameter of damage area in front of notch tip and Crack opening displacement

are generated and the status of their increase resembles the occurrence of the yielding phenomenon in the fracture toughness test of metallic material very well. Therefore, the author made it a rule to draw a circle (diameter D_p) that circumscribes the area over which surface cracks are generated and to evaluate the size of the area where damages are generated (See Figure 5 (D)).

In Figure 8, the relation among COD, the diameter D_p of the circumscribed circle and the C.D. value are present. From this figure, the circle D_p gradually increase until COD reaches the point F and eventually reaches 6.6 mm. Beyond that, the diameter of the circle expands increasingly and it is known that at the point G where COD reaches 1 mm, the diameter reaches 12 mm. However, after passing through the point G, the diameter becomes almost constant. The value of COD at the point is confirmed to coincide with 1.0 mm which is the value of COD when the stable crack began to grow as presented in the paragraph 3.2. From these experimental facts, a conclusion that it is also possible to measure the fracture toughness value J_{in} by measuring the change in the size of the circle of the area where surface cracks are generated and by confirming the position of the point G.

4. CONCLUSION

The phenomenon on the stable fracture on FRP(SMC) material has been studied. The relation between the growth of stable crack that occurs in SMC and fracture toughness value was discussed experimentally. From this results, the fracture toughness value J_{in} is given as 7.8 KN/m for used SMC material. It is confirmed that there is a strong correlation between the crack density C.D. and growth of the length of the stable crack a and it is represented by the formula $C.D. = 0.09 * a$. As the result of investigation on the relation between the surface crack density C.D. and the change of the fracture toughness value, the fracture toughness value J_{in}' is given as 8.2 KN/m. The value J_{in}' is confirmed to be very close to the fracture toughness value J_{in} . Additionally, it is confirmed that it is possible to find the fracture toughness value J_{in} by measuring the circumscribed circle of the area over which surface cracks are generated.

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